

Some Transition Metal Complexes Derived from the Heterocyclic Ligands 3-Methyl-4-Arylazopyrazole-5-Ones

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Manuscript received 8 August 1980, revised 14 July 1981, accepted 11 August 1981

Some planar and octahedral complexes of the sulphates of Cu(II) and Ni(II) with different 3-methyl-4-aryazo pyrazole-5-ones have been prepared. The complexes contain only one molecule of the ligand which functions as a bidentate donor coordinating through its carbonyl and azo group while the rest of the positions in the coordination geometry of metal are occupied by water molecules. The magnetic and electronic data of the complexes are discussed in the light of structures assigned.

THE chemistry of pyrazole-5-ones and its derivatives has attracted considerable attention of coordination chemists by virtue of their applicability as potential ligands for a large number of metal ions. It is also found that the 4-position of pyrazole-5-one system is reactive as it undergoes coupling reactions with aryl diazonium salts to furnish 4-aryazo derivatives and complexes of such azo dyes having an azole nucleus are well known¹⁻⁴. We have attempted a systematic study of the complexes derived from different pyrazole-5-ones and we report here on the synthesis of different 3-methyl-4-arylazopyrazole-5-ones and their complexes with Cu(II) and Ni(II) sulphates. The structures of the complexes have been established using analytical, conductance, magnetic, infrared and electronic spectral data.

Experimental

The title ligands have the following general structure :

and have been obtained by the following two steps :

(i) *Ethyl (phenylazo) acetoacetate* : An ice cold solution of ethyl acetoacetate (0.01 mole) in ethanol (50 ml) containing sodium acetate was mechanically stirred. A diazotised solution of various aromatic amines such as aniline, *o*-, *m*- or *p*-toluidine (0.01 mole) was gradually added while stirring and the temperature was maintained between 0-5°. The contents were further stirred for ten hrs and excess of water added. A yellow solid separated out which was left overnight filtered next morning, dried and melting point determined. The melting points and colours of the compounds are as follows :

	When x = H	m.p. °C	Colour
	x = <i>o</i> -CH ₃	57-59	Yellow
	x = <i>m</i> -CH ₃	43	Brown
	x = <i>p</i> -CH ₃	45	Brownish yellow
		72	Orange

(ii) *3-Methyl-4-(aryazo) pyrazole-5-ones* : A solution of ethyl(phenylazo) acetoacetate (0.005 mole) in glacial acetic acid was refluxed with 0.005 mole of hydrazine hydrate (or phenyl hydrazine for ligand L₅) on an oil bath at 160-170° for 5-6 hrs. The reaction mixture was left overnight. The separated solid was filtered and recrystallised from chlorobenzene.

The individual ligands prepared in the investigation are listed below along with their m.p.s and colour :

Ligand	Substituent in the ring	Name	m.p. °C	Colour
L ₁	x=H and y=H	3-methyl-4-(phenylazo) pyrazole-5-one	195	Yellow
L ₂	x= <i>o</i> -CH ₃ and y=H	3-methyl-4-(<i>o</i> -methylphenyl) azo-pyrazole-5-one	210	Yellow needles
L ₃	x= <i>m</i> -CH ₃ and y=H	3-methyl-4-(<i>m</i> -methylphenyl) azo-pyrazole-5-one	221	Yellow needles
L ₄	x= <i>p</i> -CH ₃ and y=H	3-methyl-4-(<i>p</i> -methylphenyl) azo-pyrazole-5-one	195	Yellow needles
L ₅	x=PhCH ₃ and y=Ph	1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-(<i>p</i> -methylphenylazo) pyrazole-5-one	135	Orange needles

The complexes have been prepared by refluxing Cu(II) or Ni(II) sulphate suspended in toluene with the corresponding ligand in toluene for 6-10 hrs. Toluene was distilled off and the reaction mixture allowed to cool when the complex separated out. These were recrystallised from hot toluene. The percentage yield, colour, analytical and molar conductance and magnetic moment data are given in Table I.

TABLE 1

Complexes	%M	%SO ₄	%N	%Yield	Molar conduct. in H ₂ O mhos	Colour	μ_{eff} in B.M.
1. Cu(H ₂ O) ₂ (L ₁)SO ₄	15.26 (15.93)*	23.65 (24.08)	14.60 (14.05)	78.5	Insoluble	Green	1.82
2. Cu(H ₂ O) ₂ (L ₂)SO ₄ .H ₂ O	14.90 (15.35)	21.10 (20.86)	12.86 (13.72)	80.5	130	Bluish green	1.95
3. Cu(H ₂ O) ₂ (L ₃)SO ₄	14.50 (15.35)	21.18 (20.86)	13.98 (13.72)	75.5	126	Green	1.87
4. Cu(H ₂ O) ₂ (L ₄)SO ₄	15.08 (15.35)	21.12 (20.86)	12.98 (13.72)	66.5	121	Greenish	1.90
5. Cu(H ₂ O) ₂ (L ₅)SO ₄	13.65 (12.96)	20.12 (19.60)	11.26 (11.70)	72.0	Insoluble	Bluish	2.01
6. Ni(H ₂ O) ₂ (L ₁)SO ₄	13.00 (13.65)	21.98 (22.33)	13.63 (13.05)	85.1	130	Bluish	3.49
7. Ni(H ₂ O) ₂ (L ₂)SO ₄	13.62 (13.19)	21.90 (21.38)	12.26 (12.59)	82.6	142	Green	3.20
8. Ni(H ₂ O) ₂ (L ₃)SO ₄	14.05 (13.19)	20.62 (21.58)	13.26 (12.59)	78.8	140	Green	3.42
9. Ni(H ₂ O) ₂ (L ₄)SO ₄	13.65 (13.19)	21.98 (21.38)	12.08 (12.59)	90.2	Insoluble	Greenish blue	3.31
10. Ni(H ₂ O) ₂ (L ₅)SO ₄ .H ₂ O	10.20 (11.25)	18.82 (18.43)	10.95 (10.72)	91.8	136	Bluish	3.29

*Figures in parenthesis are calculated values.

Conductivity of the complexes was measured on a Philips PR 9500 magic eye type instrument and infrared spectra were recorded in the form of nujol mulls on a Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrometer in the range 4000-400 cm⁻¹. The magnetic moments were measured by standard Gouy method on finely powdered samples, while the electronic spectra were recorded on a VSU-2P spectrophotometer in the range 220-1300 nm in the form of nujol mulls.

Results and Discussion

The molecular formulae of the complexes have been obtained from the analytical data given in the Table 1 and the molar conductance values indicate that all the complexes behave as electrolytes breaking up into two ions. The Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes are thus assigned the formulae [Cu(H₂O)₂(L₁-L₅)]SO₄ and [Ni(H₂O)₂(L₁-L₅)]SO₄ indicating that only one molecule of the ligand is added. Definite evidence for the coordination of ligands is obtained from the infrared data as discussed below :

(i) All complexes contain a strong broad band around 3400 cm⁻¹ which is the OH stretching frequency. Its negative shift is indicative of coordination⁸.

(ii) The ligand 3-methyl-4-arylazopyrazole - 5 - ones contain three possible sites of coordination, the azo linkage, the carbonyl group and the NH group. But it is not possible for all the donor sites to be coordinated to the same metal ion and hence theoretically coordination should take place from any two sites. The NH group, however, does not appear to be involved in coordination since in the spectra of free ligand L₁ to L₄ as well as their complexes a strong band appears at 3300 cm⁻¹, which is the ν NH band. The same band, however, disappears from the spectra of ligand L₅ and its complexes as expected. In the region 1550-1650 cm⁻¹ there is a wide shifting in the frequency of -N=N- and C=O groups indicating the participation of these in coordination⁹⁻¹¹. Carbonyl stretching

frequency occurs in complexes at 1635 cm⁻¹ and its negative shift from 1695 cm⁻¹ (that of free ligand) is indicative of coordination⁹. The assignment of the azo linkage has been slightly difficult as it has a tendency to get superimposed over the frequency of >C=N- grouping, but a somewhat weak band at 1570 cm⁻¹ in free ligands and at 1540 cm⁻¹ in complexes is assigned to this negative shift indicating coordination. The other bands of ligand remain intact showing that these are not involved in coordination.

(iii) The free sulphate ion belongs to the point group Td and gives two characteristic vibrations due to γ_8 and γ_4 modes. If it is involved in coordination, the symmetry is lowered to C_{3v} and other bands corresponding to γ_1 and γ_2 modes which are otherwise Raman active also appear in spectra¹⁰⁻¹¹. In the complexes two very sharp bands are seen at 1140 and 650 cm⁻¹ assigned to the γ_8 and γ_4 modes. The position of these as well as the fact that the γ_1 and γ_2 modes do not appear in the spectra confirm that the ion is not coordinated¹²⁻¹³.

These infrared data thus support the bidentate nature of the ligand which is coordinated to metal ion through carbonyl and azo groups. The coordination number of Cu(II) and Ni(II) is thus four and six as these contain two and four water molecules respectively. On the basis of magnetic and electronic spectral data the former are assigned planar and the later octahedral structures as discussed below.

Copper(II) complexes : The μ_{eff} values of the complexes lie in the range 1.8 - 2.01 B.M., and indicate the presence of one unpaired electron. In the electronic spectra two strong but broad bands are seen at around 23.50 and 12.50 kK. These spectra are similar to other planar complexes of copper(II) and the two bands may be assigned to ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g} and ²B_{1g} → ²E_g transitions respectively¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

Nickel(II) complexes : The magnetic moments for these complexes fall in the range 3.20-3.49 B.M.

suggesting spin free state. The three bands characteristic of octahedral geometry are seen at 8.60, 13.88 and 25.60 kK which are assigned to the

$\gamma_1 [3 A_{2g} \rightarrow 3 T_{1g}]$; $\gamma_2 [3 A_{2g} \rightarrow 3 T_{2g}]$ and
 $\gamma_1 [3 A_{2g} \rightarrow 3 T_{1g}]$

transitions respectively. A shoulder also occurs at 22.50 kK corresponding to the spin forbidden transition $3 A_{2g} \rightarrow 1 E_g$. The values of Dq, B and the ratio γ_2/γ_1 which are around 870 cm^{-1} , 890 cm^{-1} and 1.60 cm^{-1} respectively are in good agreement with those of other similar complexes and confirm the octahedral structures for these compounds^{17,18}.

It is further seen that the Dq values are almost similar to the values for $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4^{2+}$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$ ions and suggest that the ligands used in the study, occupy almost the same position in the spectrochemical series as water and hence replacement of water molecules causes negligible change in Dq. The nephelauxetic ratio for the complexes lie between 0.82-0.88 suggesting a high degree of covalency.

Acknowledgement

One of us (C.S.) is thankful to University Grants Commission, New Delhi for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

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